

Theory of Spacetime

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Abstract

Three hypotheses on spacetime expansion are presented. First, velocity is independent of spacetime expansion. Second, spacetime expansion does not change energy. Third, spacetime expansion is a change in size of spacetime and energy conversion is a change in shape of spacetime, or equivalent to change in velocity. These are mathematical arguments hence mathematical proofs are presented in each hypothesis. The difference in the calculation of velocity between Hubble's law and Belmonte theory is discussed. The so-called dark energy emerges as a consequence of velocity calculation in Hubble's law but it does not appear in Belmonte theory. It is shown that the cosmological constant in the general theory of relativity arises from a violation of the conservation of energy. The cosmological constant does not appear in Belmonte theory as energy is automatically conserved in the theory. Following the Second Hypothesis, the Belmonte Mass is predicted. This is the total mass of dark matter and baryonic matter in the observable universe. It is derived theoretically from the Planck vacuum energy density.

1. Introduction

Space and time were considered separate and absolute entities until in 1905 when Einstein formulated the special theory of relativity. He showed length and time vary in different inertial frames of reference. Observers in different states of motion will disagree on their measurements of length and time. Thus length and time have no universal magnitude and measurable only relative to specified reference frames. The concept of spacetime as a single entity was fully developed by Minkowski in a flat four-dimensional geometry called Minkowski spacetime.

In 1915 Einstein published the general theory of relativity based on the equivalence principle of accelerating reference frame and gravitational field. Gravity was viewed as a curvature in spacetime. The equation of general relativity implied an expanding spacetime. Einstein added a cosmological constant to the equation to stop the expansion because at that time it was generally believed that the universe is static. Friedmann formulated a solution to Einstein's equation that has a spacetime expansion and curved geometry called Friedmann spacetime or metric.

In 1929 Hubble discovered the Hubble's law that shows the universe is expanding. This is the basis of the Big Bang model of the universe. It was discovered in 1998 that the expansion of the universe is accelerating. The existence of dark energy was hypothesized to cause the observed acceleration. It is believed dark energy is equivalent to the cosmological constant in general relativity, or the vacuum energy in quantum mechanics. The true nature of dark energy remains a mystery. This paper explores the relationships of these entities in the form of a theory of spacetime.

2. Belmonte's Hypotheses

First Hypothesis:

Velocity is independent of spacetime expansion

In the concept of spacetime, space and time are inseparable. Therefore, both length expansion and time dilation must be included in the calculation of velocity.

$$v = L/t$$

$$v' = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

$$v = v'$$

$$L/t = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

Where:

v = velocity without spacetime expansion

v' = velocity with spacetime expansion

L = length without length expansion

t = time without time dilation

dL = length expansion

dt = time dilation

Proof:

Let:

z = redshift

y = wavelength

T = period or inverse of frequency

dy = change in wavelength

dT = change in period

$$v = L/t$$

$$v' = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

$$v' = L (1 + dL/L) / t (1 + dt/t)$$

$$\text{if } dL/L = dt/t, \text{ then } v = v'$$

$$z = dy/y$$

$$y/T = c$$

$$(y + dy)/(T + dT) = c$$

$$y (1 + dy/y) / T (1 + dT/T) = c$$

$$dy/y = dT/T$$

since $y = L, T = t$
then $dL/L = dt/t$

Electromagnetic waves always travel at c in a vacuum regardless of z . Therefore, length expansion and time dilation are always equal, and the velocity does not change with spacetime expansion.

In the scale factor $1 + z = R_0/R = t_0/t$
 R_0/R is a length expansion that can be written as $(L + dL)/L$
In the same manner, t_0/t is a time dilation that can be written as $(t + dt)/t$

Second Hypothesis:

Spacetime expansion does not change energy

Let:

- R = radius or distance from a massive body
- R' = radius with length expansion
- y = wavelength
- p = momentum
- h = Planck constant
- L = length without expansion
- L' = length with expansion

Scale factor in cosmological redshift

$$1 + z = R'/R$$

$$R' = R (1 + z)$$

De Broglie Equation

$$y = h/p$$

$$p y = h$$

Cosmological redshift of matter waves

$$1 + z = y'/y = L'/L$$

$$p L = k = p' L'$$

$$p' = p L/L'$$

$$p' = p/(1 + z)$$

Conservation of potential and kinetic energy:

$$G M m / R = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$$

$$G M m / R = \frac{1}{2} p v \quad \text{momentum form}$$

With spacetime expansion

$$G M m / R' = \frac{1}{2} p' v$$

$$G M m / (R (1+z)) = \frac{1}{2} v p / (1+z)$$

$$G M m / R = \frac{1}{2} p v$$

Increase in potential energy is cancelled by decrease in momentum. Hence, potential and kinetic energy is the same with and without spacetime expansion

Third Hypothesis:

Spacetime expansion is a change in size of spacetime and energy conversion is a change in shape of spacetime, or equivalent to change in velocity

Size can change without a change in shape, and vice versa

Let:

L = length

t = time

dL = change in length

dt = change in time

A = area or size

S = shape or velocity

$$A1 = L t$$

$$A2 = (L + dL) (t + dt)$$

$$S1 = L/t$$

$$S2 = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

Change in size of spacetime without change in shape:

$$A1 \neq A2$$

$$L t \neq (L + dL) (t + dt)$$

$$S1 = S2$$

$$L/t = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

Change in shape without change in size:

$$S1 \neq S2$$

$$L/t \neq (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

$$A1 = A2$$

$$L t = (L + dL) (t + dt)$$

In special relativity:

$$L + dL = L/\gamma \quad \text{length contraction, } \gamma = \text{Lorentz factor}$$

$$t + dt = t \gamma \quad \text{time dilation}$$

$$S1 < S2 \quad \text{change in shape}$$

$$L/t < (L/l)/(t l)$$

$$L/t < L/t (1/l^2)$$

$$A1 = A2 \quad \text{no change in size}$$

$$L t = (L/l) (t l) = L t$$

In general relativity, gravity and acceleration change the curvature or shape of spacetime, even in a static spacetime. Hence, change in shape is independent of change in size of spacetime

Gravitational redshift in general relativity:

$$z = y_o/y = (1 - 2 G M/(R_o c^2))^{0.5}$$

The above is equivalent to a relativistic redshift:

$$z = ((1 + v/c)/(1 - v/c))^{0.5}$$

Where the radiating body is accelerating:

$$v = a t$$

$$a = dv/t$$

Hence, gravitational redshift is equivalent to a change in velocity of a radiating body

$$z = (1 - 2 G M/(R_o c^2))^{0.5} = ((1 + dv/c)/(1 - dv/c))^{0.5}$$

3. Dark energy is relativistic kinetic energy

It is shown here that the so-called dark energy is mathematically equivalent to the relativistic kinetic energy of dark matter and baryonic matter. The rest mass is equal to the mass of dark matter and baryonic matter. The average velocity of matter is estimated by taking their average distance from Earth, which is the local rest frame. The most distant galaxy has a scale factor $(1 + z)$ of 12.1. Since matter is evenly distributed in the universe, the average distance is taken as half of 12.1 or 6.1

Relativistic kinetic energy

$$KE = m c^2 - m_o c^2 = \text{dark energy}$$

$$m = \text{relativistic mass} = \text{dark energy} + \text{dark matter} + \text{baryonic matter}$$

$$m_o = \text{rest mass} = \text{dark matter} + \text{baryonic matter}$$

Relativistic velocity

$$v/c = (1+z)^2 - 1 / (1+z)^2 + 1$$

$$\text{Average } 1 + z = 6.1$$

$$\text{Average } v/c = 0.948$$

R = ratio of dark energy to total energy

l = Lorentz factor

$$l = 1/(1 - (v/c)^2)^{0.5}$$

$$R = 1 - m_0/m = 1 - 1/\gamma = 0.682$$

This is almost equal to the observed value of 0.683 or 68.3%

4. Dark energy in Belmonte theory

In Belmonte theory, dark energy is an illusion. It emerges from an improper calculation of velocity that disregards time dilation. It results to an apparently higher velocity and higher relativistic kinetic energy, which is mathematically equivalent to dark energy. In geometric terms, spacetime expansion does not change its curvature, which means no change in gravity and velocity.

Let:

R = ratio of dark energy to total energy

m = relativistic mass

m_0 = rest mass

Hubble's law:

$$v = H_0 D$$

$$H_0 = 1/t$$

$$D = L + dL$$

$$v = (L + dL)/t$$

$$v = (1 + dL/L)/t \quad z = dL/L$$

$$v = (1 + z)/t \quad v \text{ is increasing with } z \text{ in rest frame}$$

Dark energy to total energy ratio (R)

$$R = 1 - m_0/m = 1 - 1/\gamma = 0.682$$

Belmonte's First Hypothesis:

$$v = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

$$v = L (1 + dL/L) / t (1 + dt/t)$$

$$v = L (1 + z) / t (1 + z)$$

$$v = L/t \quad v \text{ does not change with } z \text{ in comoving frame}$$

Dark energy to total energy ratio (R)

$$R = 1 - m/m = 0 \quad \text{no change in velocity, no change in relativistic mass, no dark energy}$$

5. Thought experiment on moving bodies

The table below is a thought experiment that illustrates the different ways the Hubble's law and the Belmonte theory calculate velocity. Imagine five cars moving in the same

direction and same speed (100 kph) but different starting times. The difference in starting time is dt . Hence, Car 5 is 4 hours ahead of Car 1 and so on. Each car has a trip meter that measures the distance traveled and a clock that measures the time elapsed.

The observer is in Car 1. Suppose the observer wants to calculate the speed of each car. How will he do it? Belmonte theory says look at the trip meter and clock of each car and divide the distance by time. This is the formula:

$$v = (L + dL)/(t + dt)$$

Using this formula, the velocity is 100 kph for all the cars.

Hubble's law says look at the trip meter of each car and divide the distance by the time in the clock of Car 1. This is the formula:

$$v = (L + dL)/t$$

Using this formula, the velocity is varying from 100 to 500 kph.

In terms of spacetime, Hubble's law takes into account length expansion (dL) but disregards time dilation (dt)

Reference frame	L (km)	dL (km)	t (hr)	dt (hr)	v (km/h) Hubble	v (km/h) Bel
Car 1 (observer)	100	0	1	0	100	100
Car 2	100	100	1	1	200	100
Car 3	100	200	1	2	300	100
Car 4	100	300	1	3	400	100
Car 5	100	400	1	4	500	100

6. Hubble's Law vs. Belmonte Theory

	Hubble's Law	Belmonte Theory
Geometry	Friedmann spacetime (curved)	Minkowski spacetime (flat)
Physics	General relativity	Special relativity
Frame of reference	Rest frame	Comoving frame
Time	Local time	Local time + time dilation
Mass	Increasing relativistic mass	Constant relativistic mass

The above table is a comparison between the prevailing theory following Hubble's law and Belmonte theory. Astronomical observations support the flat universe and do not rule out a zero cosmological constant. These are consistent with Belmonte theory.

“The two SNe groups (Supernova Cosmology Project and the High-z Supernova Team) gave very similar error ellipses, and the combined CMB-SNe fit indicates that a flat Universe with a cosmological constant is preferred. But the systematic errors on the SNe data... could allow for a vanishing cosmological constant λ .” (Wright, 1998)

7. Belmonte Mass

In general relativity, dark energy is the cosmological constant. This is some kind of anti-gravity or negative pressure or the vacuum energy. Anti-gravity and negative pressure are dubious. They are non-existent in the known laws of physics. Einstein added the cosmological constant to the equation of general relativity to preserve the conservation of energy because his theory predicts spacetime expansion requires energy. In Belmonte theory, it is unnecessary. Energy is conserved in spacetime expansion. No need for the cosmological constant.

General relativity predicts vacuum energy density is constant.

Vacuum energy density (Planck density)

Predicted value = $5.2 \times 10^{96} \text{ kg/m}^3$

Observed value = $6.9 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg/m}^3$

Error = 10^{122}

This is the biggest error in the history of science.

Belmonte's Second Hypothesis states that spacetime expansion does not change energy. Hence, it predicts that vacuum energy is conserved as spacetime expands from the Big Bang to the present. The Big Bang singularity is at least the size of an electron. The vacuum energy density is the density of the Big Bang. Vacuum energy was converted into gamma rays at the Big Bang and then gamma rays to leptons and quarks by pair production.

The theory predicts the Belmonte Mass, the total mass of dark matter and baryonic matter in the observable universe as derived from the Planck vacuum energy density.

Let:

B = Belmonte Mass

E_v = Planck vacuum energy density = $5.2 \times 10^{96} \text{ kg/m}^3$

V_b = volume of spacetime at Big Bang = $4\pi/3 R_e^3$

R_e = classical electron radius = $2.8 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}$

$B = E_v V_b$

Predicted value (B) = $4.8 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg}$

Observed value = $5.4 \times 10^{53} \text{ kg}$

Error = 0.12

This is much better than the prediction of the prevailing theory of dark energy and cosmological constant. Moreover, the enormous discrepancy between predicted and observed value of the vacuum energy in general theory of relativity can be reconciled using the conservation of energy principle in the Second Hypothesis.

Let:

E_v = Planck vacuum energy density = $5.2 \times 10^{96} \text{ kg/m}^3$

E_o = observed vacuum energy density = dark matter + baryonic matter

I_p = Planck intensity

v = velocity = L/t

k = constant

a = scale factor = $(R_o/R_e)^3 = 10^{123}$

R_o = radius of observable universe

R_e = classical electron radius

Conservation of vacuum energy

$I_p = E_v c^2 v = k \quad v = L/t$

$I_p = E_v c^2 (L/t) = k$

Applying the scale factor to length and time leads to conservation of vacuum energy in spacetime expansion:

$I_p = E_v c^2 (L/t) = E_v c^2 (aL/at)$

$E_v = E_v$

Applying the scale factor to length only and ignoring time dilation leads to a huge discrepancy between predicted and observed vacuum energy density:

$I_p = E_v c^2 (L/t) = E_o c^2 (aL/t)$

$E_v/E_o = a = 10^{123}$

8. Conclusion

The Belmonte theory may be viewed simply as dynamic calculations using special relativistic coordinates in a comoving frame. True but more importantly, it gives results that closely match observations. Moreover, it does not need mysterious and fantastic forces like dark energy and anti-gravity cosmological constant. There are other methods of calculation using cosmological coordinates in local rest frame. But for energy calculations, the proposed method gives the right answers. For this reason, it is elevated to a formal theory of spacetime.

The choice of coordinates and reference frame is not arbitrary. The conservation of potential-kinetic energy is violated if time dilation is excluded from the equation:

$$G M m / R = \frac{1}{2} m v^2$$

If only length expansion is included:

$$G M m / (R (1+z)) = \frac{1}{2} m (L (1+z)/t)^2$$

$$G M m / R \neq \frac{1}{2} m v^2 (1+z)^3$$

To preserve the conservation of energy, a term X must be added to the equation, which represents dark energy a.k.a. cosmological constant.

$$G M m / (R (1+z)) \neq \frac{1}{2} m (L (1+z)/t)^2$$

$$G M m / (R (1+z)) + X = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 (1+z)^2$$

Where $X = G M m / R ((1+z)^2 - 1/(1+z))$

Belmonte's Second Hypothesis shows how potential-kinetic energy is conserved in spacetime expansion without arbitrary addition of term to the equation. The particular choice of coordinates and reference frame is mandated by Belmonte theory as a law of nature.

REFERENCES

1. Dirac, Paul, General Theory of Relativity, Princeton University Press, 1996
2. Feynman, Richard, The Feynman Lectures on Physics, California Institute of Technology, 2013
3. Feynman, Richard and Weinberg, Steven, Elementary Particles and the Laws of Physics, Cambridge University Press, 1987
4. Griffiths, David; Introduction to Elementary Particles, Wiley-VCH, 2008
5. Hawking, Stephen, The Theory of Everything: The Origin and Fate of the Universe, Jaico Publishing House, 2007
6. Naber, Gregory, The Geometry of Minkowski Spacetime: An Introduction to the Mathematics of the Special Theory of Relativity, Springer-Verlag, 1992
7. Nave, C. R., HyperPhysics, Georgia State University, 2016
8. Randall, Lisa, Higgs Discovery: The Power of Empty Space, Ecco, 2013
9. Russell, Bertrand, The ABC of Relativity, New American Library, 1985
10. Wright, Edward, Cosmology Tutorial, University of California, Los Angeles, 2016
11. Young, H. D., Freedman, R. A., Sears and Zemansky's University Physics with Modern Physics, Addison-Wesley, 2000
12. Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia, Wikimedia Foundation, 2016